

**BLACK WOMEN'S (IM)MOBILITIES:
MEMORY, HISTORY AND DIASPORIC ENTANGLEMENTS¹**

Andrea A. Davis
York University, Toronto

In thinking about Black women's (im)mobilities, I am returning to and extending the ideas in my book, *Horizon, Sea, Sound: Caribbean and African Women's Cultural Critiques of Nation* (2022), to consider Black women's diasporic journeys and entanglements and how these movements across history and time transgress spatial borders and challenge the hegemonic politics of imperialist nation states. In this contemplation of memory and history, I center Canada as a space of diasporic blackness, disrupting narratives of the Black Atlantic that privilege the United States and Caribbean as the primary sources of Black historical and contemporary meaning. While Canada's official history maps a relationship to Black diasporic presences in the Americas as one of benign tolerance, Black Canadian scholars, writers and artists articulate a more nuanced and fraught relationship to the settler nation state, even as they disrupt social constructions of blackness as "the site of surprise rather than wonder" (Walcott & Abdillahi 2019, 52). Canada's history, I suggest, is deeply interwoven into the histories of the Americas and the modern world, and we cannot attend to the complexity of Black women's entangled mobilities and immobilities without considering these spatial and cultural connections.

In *Horizon, Sea, Sound*, I use the trope of the sea to reconsider historical and contemporary relationships among Black, Indian and Indigenous Caribbean women, as well as

¹ Sections of this paper are drawn from my book, *Horizon, Sea, Sound: Caribbean and African Women's Cultural Critiques of Nation* (2022).

the relationship between Canada and the Caribbean. Turning to the work of Camille Turner, M. NourbeSe Philip, and Ramabai Espinet—Caribbean artists who are now writing and thinking from Canada—as well as Guyanese British poet, Grace Nichols, I revisit and extend those arguments here by linking Canada not only to the Caribbean but also to West Africa. Specifically, I reenter this discussion of the trope of the sea by exploring the historical linkages between the Caribbean, Canada and West Africa through the archive of the ships that have sailed into and out of these various regions, connecting the Indigenous peoples of the Americas, enslaved Africans, and indentured Indians across unknowable history and time. In the process, I argue that the work of Black diasporic women artists in the Americas necessarily engages multiple Black geographies. In other words, these artists and thinkers are constantly crossing borders—physically, imaginatively and spiritually—as they negotiate and renegotiate the terms of their *being in place*. It is Africa, however, and not the Caribbean that remains a central point of both arrival and departure. I make this argument in four movements through a series of overlapping journeys from Newfoundland, Canada to Gorée Island in Senegal; Gold Coast in present day Ghana to Black River, Jamaica; St. Helena off the coast of southwestern Africa to Trinidad and Tobago; and Guyana back to Canada. These multiple and sometimes unexpected movements, I suggest, help to illustrate the deep imbrications of Black people’s interconnected journeys within and beyond the shorelines of the Americas.

Movement One: Newfoundland, Canada, to Gorée Island, Senegal

At the 2019 Bonavista Biennale held in Duntara—a small village on the Bonavista Peninsula on the east coast of Newfoundland in Canada—Jamaican-born, Toronto-based artist Camille Turner set out in her Afronautic Research Lab to present “a counter archive” of Canada’s relationship to transatlantic slavery. As she explains, “I’m really trying to map this place as a site of the black

Atlantic” (qtd. in CBC News, 2017). Some aspects of the island of Newfoundland’s role in supporting chattel slavery in the Caribbean are well known, such as the fact that salted cod was sent from Newfoundland and Labrador to what was then the British West Indies to feed enslaved African peoples working on sugar plantations, and that these plantations in turn exported refined sugar to be used in rum distilleries in the province (Walker 2012, 24). Historian Sean Cadigan (2009) confirms that from the sixteenth century, European fishermen had been lured to Newfoundland to catch and process sometimes as much as 200 tons of salted cod, most of which was exported to the Caribbean or Mediterranean (cited in Turner 2022, 50). This commercial movement between islands served to expand British interests in chattel slavery in the Americas, linking the British-colonized Caribbean and the British colony of Newfoundland, and making the white fishermen and enslaved Africans co-dependent.

What Turner attends to in her research, however, is another story that is far less known about the origins, meaning and impact of 19 slave ships built in Newfoundland and catalogued in Harvard University’s Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database.² Turner confirms in her PhD dissertation, *Unsilencing the Past: Staging Black Atlantic Memory in Canada and Beyond* (2022), that these ships, all carrying the British flag, were constructed between 1751 and 1792 and used to transport enslaved Africans from Western Africa to British colonies in the Caribbean. One ship, *Torbay*, was built in Newfoundland in 1783 and transported 245 people from Angola to Grenada in 1792. Nine of these Africans died during the journey. Another schooner, *Maria*, was built in 1785 and carried 80 people from West Africa to Grenada. Ninety-three per cent of them were children, mostly boys. Another named *Fly* was constructed in 1781. After collecting 113

² See David Eltis, et al., *Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*: <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database>.

Africans off the southwest coast of what is now Nigeria, the ship was cut off by Africans from shore, who captured the ship and freed the enslaved Africans onboard.

Turner's research thus reveals that the nation that would become Canada was not only supporting commercial trade and the movement and enslavement of Africans within the Americas, but was also involved in the heart of the slave trade itself. The British colony of Newfoundland facilitated the construction of ships used in the 18th century to transport enslaved Africans from west and southwest Africa to the Caribbean, actively participating in the colonial practices of chattel slavery far beyond its shores, and benefitting from racist and imperialist laws against Indigenous peoples and enslaved Africans. This intricate pattern of subjugation linked enslaved peoples across the British Empire, who were governed by the same British slave laws and were transported and traded constantly between the Caribbean, Canada and the United States. In 1784, the most famous enslaved woman in Canada, Marie-Joseph Angélique—who was accused of burning down Old Montréal—had initially tried to escape to New England, where she had first landed after being transported from the Portuguese island of Madeira (Cooper 2006, 179-180).

Turner attends to the deep, ongoing legacies of these interconnections by sitting with the rocks she encounters on Duntara's shores. The slave ships constructed in Newfoundland, she explains, were also ballasted with rocks from Newfoundland to ensure their stability. The ships carrying these rocks first sailed to London, Liverpool and Bristol to be registered. They then set out on journeys that took them to West Africa and finally the Caribbean. On their arrival in West Africa, the ballast was dumped onto the shore to make space for the Africans the ships would transport far away from their peoples and cultures. Rocks from Newfoundland, Turner thus contends, have been stranded across the Atlantic, and "as an archive, ballast speaks to the ways in

which space is produced through the violent entanglement of distant geographies” (58). In the video installation, *Afronautic Research Lab: Newfoundland* (2019), she walks across the shoreline carrying a rock in an act of embodied memory. As she explains in her dissertation, “[t]he character I performed and filmed walks beside the ocean, along the barren shores of Bonavista, bearing a rock that she found off the coast of West Africa but which was originally from Newfoundland” (xvii). The rock, in this sense, becomes “a stand-in for people in the hold of the ships” (116). Paying particular attention to the ways her sense of woundedness and loss is entangled with the unspoken/unspeakable memories of other African women transported across the Atlantic, Turner recalls a pivotal moment of recognition on her final trip to Gorée Island in Senegal in 2014:

As I stared through the Door of No Return one more time, contemplating the rupture that severed my ancestors from this continent, I was assaulted by a barrage of feelings. I was aware that I was at the western-most point of West Africa, and I saw—or perhaps more accurately, felt—someone staring back at me through another door on the other side of the Atlantic, a door I had yet to find. (11)

Two years later, she would unexpectedly find that other door in the Cape Spear’s lighthouse in Newfoundland, this time situated “at the eastern-most point of North America” (12). “As I peered through the door,” she recalls, “I recognized that the person I had glimpsed through the door in Senegal, on the other side of the Atlantic, was me” (12). As I note in *Horizon, Sea, Sound*, “for Caribbean women who are the descendants of enslaved Africans or indentured laborers, our access to the past is not only through memory, but also through water” (90). Water as embodied archive and living memory merges “the crosscurrents of African, Asian, and European diasporic hopes and losses” (91). But for Turner, the Atlantic does not only flow into the Caribbean Sea; it

also washes onto the shores of eastern Canada, connecting those shores unexpectedly to West Africa.

Turner's research asks us to consider what the hidden entanglements the 19 ships constructed in Newfoundland might conceal. Who were the enslaved Africans taken far from their lands on Newfoundland vessels unable to map a return home, trapped now in the afterlife of slavery's effects? Who were their kin, their people, and who carries their memories? What forgotten history do the Newfoundland rocks stranded on West African shores hold? And what about those of us now living on the land known as Canada who are the descendants of the formerly enslaved—our bodies, blood and imagination linked to multiple places, like the rocks in the Newfoundland ships, and our memories circulating still “in the time of the wake” (Sharpe 2016, 19)? The idea of discrete, politically boundaried nation states breaks apart in the presence of the logic and practice of transatlantic slavery. Newfoundland is part of the West African shoreline, as much as West Africa, through its historical and contemporary forced migrations, is part of Canada now.

Movement Two: Gold Coast, Ghana, to Black River, Jamaica

I turn next to Black River, Jamaica in 1781, the same period in which slave ships were being built in Newfoundland, to attend to another slaver, *Zong* (first called *Zorg* meaning “Care” in Dutch). Historian James Walvin in *The Zong: A Massacre, the Law and the End of Slavery* (2011), explains that *Zong* at 110 tons was small for a slave ship, and that a ship of its size would have on average transported only about 193 Africans even after factoring in the economies of profit demanded by the trade, which led to the routine overcrowding of slavers (27). Yet, when *Zong* set sail from the Gold Coast (or what is now Ghana) to Black River, Jamaica, it was carrying 459 people: 442 enslaved Africans and 17 members of crew. A voyage that was already made

precarious by this dangerous overcrowding became deadly for nearly a third of the Africans on board three weeks before finally landing in Jamaica. *Zong*, having overshoot its destination because of navigational errors, was running low on drinking water. On the order of the ship's captain, Luke Collingwood, the crew pushed at least 132 Africans overboard in three batches, drowning them in the Caribbean Sea in an attempt to ensure the crew would have access to sufficient water and that at least part of the ship's human cargo could be brought safely to land and sold (Walvin 1). Fifty-four women and children, all of them "marketable slaves" and physically healthy but deemed less valuable than men, were the first to be thrown overboard on November 29, 1781 (Burnard 2019, n.p.). The logic undergirding the murder of the Africans rested on the legal assumption that since the enslaved were property, the owners of *Zong* had a right to claim indemnity for the "murder" and disposal of their cargo—profit they would have lost if the Africans had simply died on board.

In her collection of poems *Zong!* (2008), Trinidadian Canadian poet M. NourbeSe Philip re-memories these dead Africans as an act of mourning that simultaneously reinserts their denied humanity into the historical archives and recognizes their and her agency over language as the formal text of the law and history. In re/telling this story, Philip turns to the two-page report of the court case, "Gregson v. Gilbert" and to the sea, as she explains, to "exaqua" the dead from their "liquid graves" (202). Her "recombinant antinarrative" (204) deliberately and systematically murders the text of the original case as an act of reparation and justice for the Africans, including the women and children who were murdered in this and other transatlantic crossings (193). As Philip explains, the "disorder, illogic and irrationality" of the poems symbolize the pain, confusion and disarticulation of enslaved people's suffering while also challenging and refusing the irrationality of slave law "masquerading as order, logic, and rationality" (197). In her poems,

words are broken apart, separated, repeated and clustered across pages. Elongated spaces between words and word fragments symbolize the thirsty and drowning Africans' struggle to find breath and articulate speech, as well as the limits of language. But the spaces also signal deeply buried silences—the parts of memory held in the body that “cannot be told, must be told, and will never be told” (206).

Water is a central theme in these poems. In “Zong! #1,” the entire poem is a strangled, guttural meditation on water—the source of desperate desire, deprivation, sustenance and death. The protracted syllables in the word water also suggest the question “what” (or “wat” in the Jamaican language). *Wat* legal logic could justify these murders? *Wat* ancestral guilt could justify such a punishment? In the first group of twenty-six poems, titled “Os” (meaning ‘bones’ in Latin), Philip sits metaphorically with the bones of the dead Africans—like Turner sits with the rocks in Duntara—caring for them as they were not cared for on the slave ship. Each page of these poems includes a footnote of names that commemorates the unnamed and forgotten Africans. Since these Africans were denied all singularity in the formal historical archive, including their names, Philip’s footnote stands in for that absence by providing a “footprint” to mark their aquatic presence (200), so they can be, as she explains again, “re-transformed miraculously back into human” (196). The act of questioning as a literary and archival strategy is made more explicit in “Zong! #7” where the speaker employs the investigative medium of the journalist to excavate the mysteries of the Middle Passage: “the when / the which / the who / the were” (15). By replacing the interrogative pronoun “where” with the past tense form of the verb to be, “were,” the narrative voice registers the tension between being, time and place. These Africans dead from “sour water / enemies & / want” (“Zong! #5,” 10) are denied their *being* by

the “where” and “what” and “when” of transatlantic slavery. Their being is always already conditional.

Yet, the sea, by allowing Philip to mourn—to be attentive to what Christina Sharpe calls “the wake” (2016)—and by allowing the lost to resurface and speak, provides possibilities for renewal. As Philip insists in the “Notanda” to *Zong!*, Africans’ resistance to enslavement and the erasure of their being (like the Africans who rescued the slave ship *Fly* built in Newfoundland) was fueled ultimately by the “belief and knowledge that” they always already “existed *outside of the law*” (207). And so, Philip reenters history and the archive in another way to account for African *being*: the “who” and “were” of chattel slavery. In the process, she reveals not only the “when” of history, but also what the past has made possible (Alexander 2005, 278).

Philip, like Turner, also asks us to reflect on those who remain. Like the Africans on *Torbay* and the children on *Maria* who landed in Grenada, where are the ancestors of the remaining Africans on *Zong* who were miraculously allowed to live, landing on shore in Black River, Jamaica on December 22, 2018? Philip asks, “How did they – the Africans on board the *Zong* – make meaning of what was happening to them? What meaning did they make of it and how did they make it mean” (194)? Who still mourns for the women and children, made dispensable because of their race, gender, age and origins in Africa? Do their bereft ancestors wander the streets of Toronto, Montréal or Newfoundland in the twenty-first century, and can they ever recover from even the hint of the memory of such a catastrophe?

Movement Three: St. Helena to Trinidad and Tobago

The Indo-Trinidadian Canadian poet and novelist Ramabai Espinet explores a different set of diasporic entanglements in her novel *The Swinging Bridge* (2003). These entanglements appear in the novel’s engagement of the Atlantic Ocean and *kala pani* as sites of the interconnecting

histories of Africans and Indians transported to the Caribbean as enslaved and indentured workers. Caribbean feminist scholar Rhoda Reddock (1986) explains that the post-slavery labor recruitment strategy known as Indian indentureship began as soon as slavery was abolished in British colonies between 1834 and 1838.³ Between 1838 and 1839, approximately 6,000 men and 100 women were transported from Calcutta and Madras bound for indentured labor in Mauritius, Australia and British Guiana, now Guyana (Reddock 27). Indian indentureship in Trinidad began later in 1845 with the last ship, the *S.S. Ganges*, arriving on the island in April 1917 (Shah 2017, n.p.). Having crossed the *kala pani* or ‘black waters,’ Indian indentured servants, like the formerly enslaved, were cut off from their people and denied any genuine possibility of return.

In *The Swinging Bridge*, Espinet links African Middle Passage memories and *kala pani* histories through Jeevan, the Indian character who, during the novel’s fictional 1879 voyage, kills a white sailor to protect a young Hindu widow from rape. Espinet’s fictional indentureship vessel, *Artist*, having sailed out of the Bay of Bengal into the Indian Ocean and then around the southern tip of Africa into the south Atlantic Ocean, makes its first stop at St. Helena, a small remote British colony under the control of the East India Company. Here Jeevan is taken off board and is either exiled or killed. Espinet explains in an interview with Elaine Savory (2007), that for these voyages that lasted approximately 100 days at sea, “St. Helena was a necessary stop for the ships after the battering off the Cape of Good Hope” (88). But, perhaps even more importantly, the island also became an important contact zone between those Africans and Indians who would eventually end up in the Caribbean. Before the British abolition of slavery, St. Helena relied on African chattel slavery with enslaved Africans from East Africa and Madagascar

³ The British Slavery Abolition Act took effect on August 1, 1834, but provided immediate emancipation only for children under the age of six in the Caribbean where enslaved Africans were tied to their enslavers for an additional four years during a period of apprenticeship. The period of apprenticeship did not apply to enslaved people in Canada. See Government of Canada, *The Enslavement of African People in Canada (c. 1629–1834)*, July 31, 2020.

making up a larger number of the island's inhabitants than white or free Black people (Fox 2017). In the beginning of the eighteenth century, the East India Company expanded its trade in human chattel, also employing enslaved Asian laborers from India and Malaysia (Fox 2017, n.p.). In addition, between 1840 and 1874, five years before the setting in Espinet's novel, approximately 30,000 Liberated Africans, rescued from slave ships after the British abolition of slavery, were brought to the island. At least eight thousand, close to death from disease, starvation and lack of water died and remain buried on the island with no marker or commemoration (Selkirk 2017, n.p.). In 2008, the bones of 325 of these Africans, including young children, were excavated by archaeologists who believe they are among "the last trace of the estimated 1.8 million people who perished in the Middle Passage" (Selkirk 2017, n.p.). Those who survived were sent as indentured servants to British Guiana, Jamaica and Trinidad. The "liberation" of these Africans, which was only a continuation of their unfreedom, mapped their ongoing suffering like that of the many before them, dispersing them and their generations far from any original home into an unknowable abyss.

This is the island on which Espinet's character, Jeevan, disappears without a trace, his memory and history forever intertwined with those of the dispossessed Africans and Indians who died there. He is also connected across the Atlantic to a Caribbean he will never know through the Africans who survived and were transported there and a young Indian widow, whose life he saves and who mourns him perpetually. Jeevan's exile on the island is, thus, a powerful metaphor of the transoceanic links between the Middle Passage and *kala pani* and the shared traumatic histories of chattel slavery and indentureship that continue to hover over contemporary Caribbean life. As an expert in stick-fighting martial art, Jeevan is further connected to a long tradition of African resistance in the Caribbean through the history of Calinda, the stick-fighting art in

Trinidad and Tobago that emerged from the African celebration of Canboulay and later Carnival. Jeevan's link to St. Helena finally connects him to Ma Touissant, another character in the novel who "claims a direct line of descent from free Africans who had been bought as indentures" (Espinet 2003, 288), possibly from the South Atlantic island of St. Helena, after slavery was abolished.

In these subtle but powerful textual moves, Espinet connects the Africans in the Caribbean mourning for their unmarked dead to Indian widows singing *Ramayana* in the rain. Their call and response, as a relational practice of survival, reverberates as a chorus, enunciating an unspeakable shared loss of community, language, history and memory, as well as shared resistance and hope. This practice of relationality recognizes that freedom for Black peoples is dependent on freedom for other oppressed peoples of the world, and acknowledging the ways in which the sea is deeply interwoven into African and Indian Caribbean histories opens up new ways of theorizing the sea that make space for these relational practices of survival.

Hofman, Bright and Ramos (2010) argue further that rather than cutting off and insulating the region's islands into discrete, secluded land forms and communities, the Caribbean Sea actually linked pre-Columbian Indigenous communities to one another and facilitated human mobility and the exchange of goods and ideas:

The highly variegated pre-Colonial Caribbean (is)landscape, always had a dynamic, inter-connected character thanks to the maritime orientation of its native (Amerindian) inhabitants and the regionwide interaction networks they maintained. It is now commonly accepted that human islanders were never socially isolated except in very extreme cases, but rather that the sea likely

functioned as an ‘aquatic motorway’, a plane that the islanders would have traversed frequently, despite its occasional unpredictability. (2)

This understanding of the sea’s simultaneous function as land, sky, and water underscores the social and cultural geographies of islands, disrupting an understanding of the Caribbean that relies on binary conceptions of sea and land, island and continent, routedness and rootedness and moving us toward a more archipelagic sense of self and space.

I am drawing here on Vincente Diaz’s (2015) notion of an archipelagic way of knowing that recognizes “the deep and profound kinship between humans and the animal world as well as the genealogical connections between humans and animals on the one hand [and] land and sea on the other” (96). This sense of connectedness between land and sea challenges the binary assumption that Black diasporic histories are solely marked by water while Indigenous histories are rooted in struggles over land. When we accept that pre-Columbian Indigenous peoples were seafarers and resituate them as the original discoverers and inhabitants of the Caribbean, we open up the trope of the sea beyond a diasporic reading of African and Indian Caribbean displacement and loss to make room for a conceptualization of what it means to live in relation to place; in other words, to consider what happens after one lands.

Movement Four: Guyana to Canada

In this final consideration of what it means to *be in place*, I make one last move to the mainland Caribbean nation of Guyana—a shared site of memory for Caribbean Indigenous peoples, enslaved Africans and Indian indentured servants, whose descendants would have made up the large proportion of Caribbean peoples migrating to Canada in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. In this move, I consider the arrival of Columbus’s ships and his landing, which

marked the beginning of the formal history of these so-called “new worlds,” conquered first for the Spanish monarchy in a series of violent disappearing acts that estranged Indigenous peoples from their land and locked them in a forgotten and misremembered past. What did the Indigenous peoples of the Caribbean make of the first sighting of the *Pinta*, *Niña*, and *Santa María* as they pulled within sight of *Guanahini* / San Salvador Island on October 12, 1492? Did they get a glimpse of the horror the sea carried? And what did they make of each subsequent emergence from the sea of European enslavers, clergy, and merchants; of shackled and enslaved Africans; of soon to be brutalized indentured workers? Resituating the Caribbean Indigenous peoples as witnesses to the catastrophic past and repositories of Caribbean Sea memories, allows a recognition of the Caribbean as both sea *and* land, as a place where people lived for thousands of years before Columbus’s arrival, and a place of contemporary life for millions of people—not just as a place of diasporic arrival or departure.

I invoke this sense of land in the way Shanya Cordis (2019) defines it “as embedded within power-laden spaces of social, spiritual, and cultural attachments and claims to belonging” (28). As the place of departure and arrival, as well as a place of living and continuing subjugations, the Caribbean functions as an apt metaphor of the entanglements of European conquest, African enslavement and Indian indentureship. It also registers diasporic routedness *and* the rootedness of those Africans and Indians who cannot or do not wish to leave, as well as the presence of long-established Indigenous communities. In other words, practices of survival and ways of living through reciprocal relationship among the various oppressed peoples of the Americas have long been made compulsory by the forces of colonialism and imperialism.

To register this sense of Caribbean women’s interdependence, or what Shanya Cordis calls “relational difference” (30), I turn in the second chapter of my book to the Guyanese poet

Grace Nichols and her collection of poems *I Have Crossed an Ocean* (2010) to think about how one might enact these shared histories. These poems draw on Nichols's Guyanese roots to center African, Indian and Caribbean Indigenous women's presence in the region as a dual relationship to land and sea. The poems are narrated through the powerful persona of Cariwoma, who is a complex representation of Caribbean women's intersecting histories and oppressions. She is simultaneously the Indigenous ancestress keeping guard over the land and sea, and the African diasporic mother who is a witness to her generations' historical and contemporary subjugations.

In the poem, "I, Cariwoma Watched History Happen," Cariwoma appears as a two-headed Janus, a witness to both the histories of Indigenous conquest and African enslavement. As a two-headed spirit, she is the Indigenous guardian of the shore, who witnesses the arrival of the conquistadors, but she is also the African foremother bearing witness to the enslavement and ongoing unfreedom of her generations. In the poem's first stanza, as the Indigenous guardian, her head rises from her hammock on the Caribbean shore and turns toward the Caribbean Sea, where she witnesses the arrival of Columbus's ships—the *Niña*, *Pinta* and *Santa María*—and discerns the horror they bring in their wake. In the poem's second stanza, her other head rises from within the bowels of a slave ship and swivels back like a *douen*—the faceless Caribbean plantation spirit whose feet are turned permanently backwards. This head gazes back at the past, "at the shards of broken pots, / the waves of palmwine betrayal" (132). Body facing forward and feet and head facing backward, Cariwoma is connected to multiple places and histories, desiring an unrecoverable past. Unable to map a return across the Middle Passage, she joins the other half of herself on shore, "the eyes of the sea-almonds" beckoning "a cautious welcome across new shores" (132).

Since she is also the repository of Black women's pain, Cariwoma mourns, like Philip and Turner, for the dead Africans. Re-narrating Columbus's gospel of salvation, she locates heaven in the underbelly of the sea: "In my sea-house there are many mansions / Who knows more than me / the songs of the drowning" ("In My Sea-House," 134)? She guards the living, even as she commemorates the dead to whom she offers a homage "of continuous remembering" (134). As the embodiment of the dual spirits of Caribbean Indigenous and African women, Cariwoma also witnesses the arrival of other ships carrying indentured laborers—Indian, Chinese, Portuguese, and Irish. The Atlantic, *kala pani*, and Sargasso Sea flow into the Caribbean Sea and the shorelines of the Guianas. Each Crossing demands a new reckoning of the land, water, and air—a consideration of the means by which survival was, and is, possible under conditions of conquest. In the Caribbean, bounded by the sea and ocean, African, Indian and European histories, dreams and memories converge: "Their song of exile / their drums of loss / all caught in a weaving odyssey / of no return" (133).

Cariwoma, however, bequeaths to her diasporic children scattered across the globe, like "migrating spider birds" ("My Children are Movers," 129), a commitment to living and survival. The sky, as the new mode of globalized travel, is linked through history to the sea, as Cariwoma's children create new "triangulars across Atlantic" (129), migrating to Canada, the United States and Europe. The sky / sea facilitates migration to far-away horizons, registering the depth of Cariwoma's separation from her children who are everywhere and nowhere. Diasporic dispersal brings a new kind of terror—the slave and indenture ship replaced by the airplane that sucks whole families abroad across "the glittering sea we call sky" ("Old Canecutter at Airport," 147). Cariwoma's diasporic children's rejection of what they perceive as island stasis and underdevelopment reflects their deep investment in the illusive promise of capitalist progress.

The equally deep sense of loss occasioned by their physical and psychological departures is etched permanently in the face of an Indian canecutter, “a study of diasporic brooding” (“Old Canecutter at Airport,” 147). The grandfather mourns a new *kala pani* loss, wailing for his only grandson departing for Canada to join his mother and wailing also for the ancestors lost to history and time.

Concluding Thoughts

In this paper, I have tried to register the ways in which Canada’s history and present are entangled in the wider histories of the Americas and the world. Black people were enslaved in Canada, as they were across the British Empire, and enslaved peoples across the Americas were connected and remain connected to each other in ways that are impossible to fully understand. The waters of the Atlantic flow from the northeast coast of the island of Newfoundland to the shores of West Africa, and rocks from Newfoundland are scattered across the coasts of West Africa from the 19 slave ships that connected these two places. The Atlantic Ocean flows into the Caribbean Sea and is also the body of water into which Guyana’s rivers and the major rivers of the South American mainland flow, with their clay minerals settling deep into the bottom of the Caribbean Sea (Menziés & Ogden 2019, n.p.). The Atlantic Ocean and the Caribbean Sea, and the ships that traverse them, connect Canada to West Africa and the Caribbean, and the Caribbean islands to the South American continent where Caribbean Indigenous peoples still live. These circulating journeys mark ongoing neocolonial struggles over people, land and resources. In light of this deep connectedness, how might Black women who are the descendants of Africans formerly enslaved in the Americas understand our shared responsibility to live in relation with each other for the protection of the environment and for the creation of a more just world? In summer 2023, major news outlets reported that Canadian wildfire smoke had reached

Europe, extending as far as Norway. Cut off from Africa and deposited in cities across the world, what if we understood belonging not merely in terms of loyalty to a desired nation state and instead imagined new affiliations of community that are wide, expansive and inclusive? Unsettling diaspora's investment in the idea of a singular democratic, egalitarian nation state—the idea of an idealized homeland located in the past or present—as essential to a realization of being, recognizes that we are not only connected to other places, people and times but that we are accountable to a global community. This commitment to work collectively with the world's people for racial and environmental justice, to ensure we survive beyond the dystopic future, supersedes loyalty to any singular nation state and demands cooperation, flexibility, adaptability and a willingness to heed Audre Lorde's (1984) call that we recognize each other “across our human differences as equals” (115). By refusing to be contained, and by resisting imposed “hierarchies of the human” (Walcott 2018, 75), Black women may finally be able to model more equitable forms of nonhierarchical citizenship that might allow us to live free without denying anyone else's right to life.

Works Cited

- Alexander, Jacqui M. 2005. *Pedagogies of Crossing: Meditations on Feminism, Sexual Politics, Memory*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Burnard, Trevor. 2019. “A New Look at the Zong Case of 1783.” *XVII-XVIII: Revue de la Société D'études Anglo-Américaines des XVIIe et XVIIIe Siècles* 76, n.p.
<https://doi.org/10.4000/1718.1808>.
- Cadigan, Sean T. 2009. *Newfoundland and Labrador: A History*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press. <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442688704>.

- CBC News. 2019. "Artist highlights N.L.'s slave trade connection in Bonavista exhibition." *CBC News*, August 18, 2019. <https://www.cbc.ca/news/canada/newfoundland-labrador/camille-turner-nl-slave-ships-connection-1.5240589>.
- Cooper, Afua. 2006. *The Hanging of Angelique: The Untold Story of Canadian Slavery and the Burning of Old Montreal*. Toronto: Harper Perennial.
- Cordis, Shanya. 2019. "Forging Relational Difference: Racial Gendered Violence and Dispossession in Guyana." *Small Axe* 23 (3): 18-33.
- Davis, Andrea A. 2022. *Horizon, Sea, Sound: Caribbean and African Women's Cultural Critiques of Nation*. Evanston, Illinois: Northwestern University Press.
- Diaz, Vincente M. 2015. "No Island is an Island." In *Native Studies Keywords*, edited by Stephanie Nohelani Teves, Andrea Smith, and Michelle H. Raheja, 90-108. Tucson: University of Arizona Press.
- Eltis, David, et al. 2008. *Trans-Atlantic Slave Trade Database*. Harvard University. <https://www.slavevoyages.org/voyage/database>.
- Espinete, Ramabai. 2003. *The Swinging Bridge*. Toronto: Harper Flamingo Canada.
- Fox, Colin. 2017. *A Bitter Draught: St. Helena and the Abolition of Slavery 1792-1840*. Elveden: Society of Friends of St. Helena.
- Government of Canada. 2020. *The Enslavement of African People in Canada (c. 1629–1834)*, July 31, 2020. <https://www.canada.ca/en/parks-canada/news/2020/07/the-enslavement-of-african-people-in-canada-c-16291834.html>.
- Hofman, Corine L., Alistair J. Bright, and Reniel Rodríguez Ramos. 2010. "Crossing the Caribbean Sea: Towards a Holistic View of Pre-Colonial Mobility and Exchange."

- Journal of Caribbean Archaeology*, Special Publication, no. 3: 1-18. https://www.floridamuseum.ufl.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/44/2017/04/Hofman_etal.pdf.
- Menzies, Robert James and John C. Ogden. 2019. "Caribbean Sea." *Encyclopedia Britannica*. <https://www.britannica.com/place/Caribbean-Sea>.
- Nichols, Grace. 2010. *I Have Crossed an Ocean: Selected Poems*. Hexham, UK: Bloodaxe Books.
- Philip, M. NourbeSe. 2008. *Zong!* Middletown: Wesleyan University Press.
- Reddock, Rhoda. 1986. "Indian Women and Indentureship in Trinidad and Tobago 1845-1917: Freedom Denied." *Caribbean Quarterly* 32, no. 3-4: 27-49.
- Savory, Elaine. 2007. "Interview with Ramabai Espinet." *Wadabagei* 10, no. 2: 82-96.
- Selkirk, Diane. 2017. "The Bones of St. Helena: Two Cinematographers are capturing the secret history of a South Atlantic island full of the bones of Liberated Africans." *Pacific Standard*. January 10, 2017. <https://psmag.com/magazine/the-bones-of-st-helena>.
- Shah, Ryhaan. 2017. "The Last Ship." *Guyana Times* April 16, 2017. <https://guyanatimesgy.com/the-last-ship/>
- Sharpe, Christina. 2016. *In the Wake: On Blackness and Being*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Turner, Camille Joy. 2022. "Unsilencing the Past: Staging Black Atlantic Memory in Canada and Beyond." PhD dissertation, York University. <http://hdl.handle.net/10315/39696>.
- Walcott, Rinaldo. 2018. "Against Social Justice and the Limits of Diversity: or Black People and Freedom." *Toward What Justice? Describing Diverse Dreams of Justice in Education*, edited by Eve Tuck and K. Wayne Yang, 68–79. New York: Routledge, 2018.
- Walcott, Rinaldo, and Idil Abdillahi. 2019. *BlackLife: Post-BLM and the Struggle for Freedom*. Winnipeg: ARP Books.

Walker, Barrington. 2012. "Jamaicans and the Making of Modern Canada." *Jamaica in the Canadian Experience: A Multiculturalizing Presence*, edited by Carl E. James and Andrea Davis, 23-34. Halifax: Fernwood Publishing.

Walvin, James. 2011. *The Zong: A Massacre, the Law and the End of Slavery*. New Haven: Yale University Press.